

Editorial

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Knowledge-based human society is a new stage in the development of our human civilization, a stage that is in a new development, from a qualitative point of view, of the way of life, a state of affairs that involves the widespread use of information and knowledge in all spheres of the social activities palette. For the human society of knowledge an unquestionable value is scientific knowledge and its fruits or its product, or scientific knowledge. Thus, for the development of human society, based on scientific knowledge acts, both scientific knowledge itself and culture, from the perspective of the scientific context, are the most important issues to be included in the general knowledge of society (Turcan 2011, 35).

Scientific communication is nothing more than the exchange of information, ideas and discoveries among scientists, which Leo Meltzer also defines as the totality of means, publications, institutional activities and any other channels of information transmission, as well as habits that, either directly or indirectly, affects

the transmission of scientific messages between scientists (Kaplan 1968, 112). Leo Meltzer states that this way of communication is different from ordinary, everyday communication, communication about physical reality that only refers to generalized and encoded knowledge. Each communication, ideally, contributes through the information palette brought to the formation of the knowledge patrimony, unanimously accepted and identified as specific aspects of science, which is achieved in particular by expanding the research limits and if necessary by modifying the hypotheses outlined above, along with additional explanations or verification of existing and accepted knowledge in the scientific world (Türcan 2011, 37).

Scientific communication can take two forms, namely communication between scientists, or simply informational communication, the communication of research results, in various communication possibilities provided by the informational means of the international information flow. As scientists exchange information among themselves, it gives a social dimension to the process of knowledge, while only informational communication, of the research results, gives a dimension of content about knowledge. When both dimensions, namely the social dimension (communication between scientists) and the informational dimension of content, are met, we are dealing with an internal scientific communication, while only the communication of the research results, based on the informational communication through various channels for information media is an external scientific communication (Watzlawick 1967, 296; Türcan 2011, 37).

According to Bryant Chris's (2003, 357-361) vision, scientific communication is nothing but a summary of all the ways and processes by which scientific knowledge alongside cultural values is absorbed and incorporated into the great cultural palette of society and thus both knowledge and scientific culture become part of general human knowledge.

Our modern world, according to Nelly Turcan (2010, 26) is nothing but „the direct or indirect product of science, and the speed of progress in science has always been strongly dependent on how scientists can communicate effectively to colleagues about research results and identify individuals who want to implement these results in new technologies and practices. Modern science has crystallized at the intersection of practical, social and cultural experiences of great complexity ... Science is a complex social phenomenon that depends on several other phenomena of social life ... As a social system, science can exist only in the interaction and linkage between the constituent elements: human resources, embedded in scientific research; ideas, facts, theories and methods of research; scientific literature; instrumentation for scientific research. Whilst knowledge is generally linked to an individual, scientific research, the purpose of which is to obtain, accumulate and interpret scientific information, is a collective activity; it is related to the communicative interaction between researchers. Only when knowledge is transmitted and accessible to the scientific community for validation and use in later research, this knowledge becomes scientific and provides knowledge.”

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